

B.I.P. Measurement with Neosepta* Membranes (Anion Exchangers) for Some Common Pairs of Anions in Electrolytic Solutions

S. K. SAHARAY and A. S. BASU

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104, India

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B. I. P. s of different anion pairs $\text{Br}^- - \text{Cl}^-$, $\text{I}^- - \text{Cl}^-$, $\text{I}^- - \text{Br}^-$, $\text{NO}_3^- - \text{Cl}^-$, $\text{NO}_3^- - \text{Br}^-$, $\text{NO}_3^- - \text{I}^-$ and $\text{NO}_3^- - \text{IO}_3^-$ have been studied using the methods of Sollner and Wyllie with the three anion-exchange membranes AV-3, AV-3T and AVS-3T of the 'Neosepta' family.

The idea of the constancy of the 'intramembrane mobility ratio' which is truly a membrane property, is justified. The magnitudes of the mobility ratio values indicate that the absolute mobilities follow the sequence in the increasing order as $U_{\text{I}^-} > U_{\text{Br}^-}$

$U_{\text{NO}_3^-} > U_{\text{Cl}^-} > U_{\text{IO}_3^-}$ which is alike to the earlier observations with other different types of membranes. Moreover, the mobility ratio values obtained in the two methods are in excellent agreement with each other indicating that they are un-influenced by any secondary phenomenon like water transport.

THE potential difference across a permselective membrane which separates two solutions containing different critical ions has been termed bi-ionic potential (B.I.P.). The studies on B.I.P. reveal some interesting aspects of membrane electrodes, viz. the relative selectivity of the membranes for different counter ions, their permeabilities and the intramembrane 'mobility' or 'transference number' ratios¹⁻⁸.

In this investigation the B.I.P.'s have been studied with the 'Neosepta' membranes⁹ comparing the two methods of measurements, which may be called the method of Sollner¹ and the method of Wyllie¹⁰, with the purpose to establish if these membranes also follow the same general observations with the other types of membranes used by earlier workers^{10,11}.

Experimental

The two sides of the membranes are converted into the respective bi-ionic forms following the procedure of some pioneer workers like Sollner¹ and Wyllie¹⁰. The three anion exchange membranes used in these studies are AV-3, AV-3T and AVS-3T. Accepting the arbitrary non-thermodynamic assumptions of single ion activity^{12,13} the standard solutions of electrolytes, all being the potassium salts, were so prepared that the activities of the successive solutions maintain a constant ratio 3 : 1 with one another. The emf.s were read within ± 0.1 mv with the help of a Cambridge potentiometer with a suspended coil galvanometer having a current sensitivity of 10^{-10} amp./mm/m. All measurements

were taken at the temperature, $25 \pm 1.0^\circ$. The solutions on the two sides were changed frequently until further renewal caused practically no change in potentials observed. The average value of several readings of a particular pair not varying more than 2% was accepted. The functional asymmetry is also tested with a few membranes in the B.I.P. studies by reversing the ionic form of the membrane sides and taking similar measurements. The membranes have been found to be more or less symmetrical, and a slight asymmetry does not affect the average value.

The membrane potentials are measured with the conventional set up of the cell¹¹

where S.C.E.s are the saturated calomel electrodes with satd. KCl-agar bridges.

The expression for the B.I.P. is

$$E_{\text{B.I.P.}} = \frac{2.303 RT}{(-)nF} \log \frac{a_x \bar{U}_x}{a_y \bar{U}_y} \quad \dots (1)$$

where \bar{U}_x/\bar{U}_y denotes the 'intramembrane mobility ratio', a_x and a_y the activities of X^- and Y^- ions of electrolytic solutions on the two sides of the membrane.

As regards the sign of B.I.P. the usual convention of early workers^{1,4,14} was followed, viz. the more

* Membranes received as gift samples from Dr. Y. Mizutani, Tokuyama Soda Company, Japan

mobile ion impresses its own sign of charge on the opposite solution, which will be evident from the sign of the reference electrodes. Two methods were followed in these B.I.P. studies.

1. Method of Sollner¹ :

B.I.P.s were studied from a higher to a lower concentration range but keeping the activity ratio of the two sides always unity. The entire range of study is within the range of Nernstian response^{1,5}.

The equation (1) will be reduced to

$$E = \frac{2.303 RT}{(-)nF} \log \frac{\bar{U}_X}{\bar{U}_Y} \quad \dots\dots(2)$$

where B.I.P. is directly related to \bar{U}_X/\bar{U}_Y .

2. Method of Wyllie¹⁰ :

B.I.P. values for each pair were recorded with the activity of one ion fixed and varying the other ion and vice versa, and thus two series of e.m.f.s were obtained. With a view to the earlier observations^{1,5}, the activity of the 'fixed ion' was so selected that the ratio must lie within the limiting value to minimise the effect of water transport. The highest and the lowest values were fixed within the range of Nernstian response. When plotted E versus the logarithm of activity, the potentials fall on two straight lines. Both straight lines should show the magnitude of slope values equal to $2.303RT/nF$ or 59.16 for uni-uni system at 25°. The mobility ratio values are calculated from the point of cutting of either of these two straight lines with the abscissa, where $E=0$ and $a_Y/a_X = \bar{U}_X/\bar{U}_Y$. Accordingly, two values of \bar{U}_X/\bar{U}_Y are obtained from each set of plots. In most cases the ratios, calculated from two different sets of a_Y/a_X values, are not identical and the arithmetic average of the two is recorded. Theoretically, the point of intersection of the two straight lines should actually be the exact middle point of the two points at which the two lines cut the abscissa. But in practice, this is not always so due to the deviations in their slope values.

Results and Discussion

As mentioned the B.I.P.s of the different anion pairs, $\text{Br}^- - \text{Cl}^-$, $\text{I}^- - \text{Cl}^-$, $\text{I}^- - \text{Br}^-$, $\text{NO}_3^- - \text{Cl}^-$, $\text{NO}_3^- - \text{Br}^-$, $\text{NO}_3^- - \text{I}^-$ and $\text{NO}_3^- - \text{IO}_3^-$ are studied, with the three anion exchange membranes AV-3, AV-3T and AVS-3T following both the methods of Sollner and Wyllie. The range of activity studied is from $a=0.0729$ to $a=0.0009$.

B.I.P. values obtained by Sollner method are graphically represented with a typical membrane AV-3T by figure 1 (A & B). The e.m.f. values are more or less constant as expected from equation (2), but variations occur at the dilute range. This variation was also noted by Sollner¹ and clearly

indicates that the process becomes partially film diffusion controlled.

Fig. 1. Plots of B. I. P. values (Sollner method) of different uni-uni anion pairs against the logarithm of activities with the anion exchanger AV-3T membrane.

Results obtained in the method 2 (Wyllie method) with a typical membrane AV-3T are shown in the figure 2, where the excellent straight line plots in accordance with the expectations are obtained.

When the ratio exceeds the limiting values as observed with concentration potentials^{1,5}, the deviations from the straight lines are observed.

Slope values for the anion pairs with the membrane AV-3T mentioned on the Figure 2 show slight deviations from the exact theoretical value 59.2. However, considering the limitations involved in the B.I.P. measurements and the assumptions in the derivation of the Wyllie's equation it may be said that on the average the general observations are in good agreement with the expectations. In this connection, it may be said that much more deviations were observed by Bergsma and Staverman⁶. These deviations may be due to water transport, a fact which seems to be the major cause in view of earlier investigations^{1,5} with these membranes. Moreover in the derivation of Wyllie's equation the conception of complete membrane diffusion control is implied. The possibility that these bi-ionic systems are likely to be partially film-controlled for which the deviations are likely to occur has been suggested by Helfferich⁷.

The average 'intramembrane mobility ratio' values obtained by Sollner method and those found by Wyllie method are tabulated in the Table 1.

The most remarkable part of these studies of B.I.P.s by the two methods are revealed in the Table 1, which show that in spite of the limitations involved in both the methods, the mobility ratio values are in excellent agreement with each other.

Fig. 2. Plots of B.I.P. values (Wyllie method) of different uni-uni anion pairs against the logarithm of activities with AV-3T membrane. Slope values are in parenthesis.

Br⁻-Cl⁻→○ (59.4, 58.3), I⁻-Br⁻→△ (60.0, 58.3),
 I⁻-Cl⁻→□ (62.2, 60.3), NO₃⁻-Cl⁻→⊗ (55.9, 55.0),
 Br⁻-NO₃⁻→(53.4, 47.0), I⁻-NO₃⁻→⊗ (54.0, 52.0),
 NO₃⁻-IO₃⁻→○ (54.7, 47.0).

TABLE I—COMPARISON OF THE MOBILITY RATIO VALUES OBTAINED BY THE METHODS OF (SOLLNER AND WYLLIE) MEASUREMENTS WITH THE THREE ANION EXCHANGER MEMBRANES

Sl. No.	Mobility Ratio	Sollner Method			Wyllie Method		
		AV-3	AV-3T	AVS-3T	AV-3	AV-3T	AVS-3T
1.	U _{Br⁻} /U _{Cl⁻}	1.09	1.12	1.39	1.08	1.09	1.33
2.	U _{I⁻} /U _{Cl⁻}	2.90	1.69	2.27	2.68	1.54	2.36
3.	U _{I⁻} /U _{Br⁻}	1.91	1.24	1.49	1.93	1.20	1.45
4.	U _{NO₃⁻} /U _{Cl⁻}	1.01	1.03	1.27	1.03	1.09	1.16
5.	U _{Br⁻} /U _{NO₃⁻}	1.10	1.09	0.87	1.15	1.12	0.87
6.	U _{I⁻} /U _{NO₃⁻}	2.50	1.57	1.83	2.74	1.99	1.86
7.	U _{NO₃⁻} /U _{IO₃⁻}	1.64	1.58	—	1.58	1.46	—

In fact, in the Wyllie method of measurements, the relatively large difference in the activities of the solvents in the two solutions separated by a

membrane is manifested only in the deviations of the slope values and does not appear in practice to affect the mobility ratio values.

The sign of the B.I.P.s and the magnitude of the mobility ratio values, obtained in both the methods, clearly indicate that the resultant mobility of the halide ions in each of the three membranes follow the order U_{I⁻}>U_{Br⁻}>U_{Cl⁻}. The mobility sequence is in conformity with the earlier observations of Sollner¹ with protamine collodion membranes and of Basu¹¹ with heterogeneous ion exchange resin membranes. It is also interesting to note that in strong base anion exchange resins the selectivity for the halide ions follows the same sequence, I⁻>Br⁻>Cl⁻, although the hydrodynamic sizes and ion-conductances of these ions in aqueous solutions are almost the same^{16,17}.

The question that naturally arises is 'how is it that the more adsorbable ion becomes the more mobile ion?' Apparently it seems that more adsorbable ion should be the less mobile ion due to its strong binding within the membrane phase. However, the situation in the studies on the selectivity with resin beads is different from the situation in the bi-ionic potential with the membranes. In case of B.I.P. studies the membrane phase is saturated with the two counter ions, and it is quite likely that there will be non-uniform distribution of the two types of counter-ions due to difference in selectivity. Assuming no Sieve effect due to very large size of the ions, it may be presumed that greater the adsorbability the greater will be the abundance of that particular ion.

It may now be explained, in the light of Wyllie's relation¹¹,

$$\frac{\bar{U}_X}{\bar{U}_Y} = K_Y \frac{x \bar{k}_X}{k_Y} \dots (3)$$

where the mobility ratio is related to the selectivity term K_Y^X and the conductivities \bar{k}_X and \bar{k}_Y of the membrane in the respective ionic forms. If the K_Y^X becomes the more influential factor as in the case of I⁻ with respect to Br⁻ or Cl⁻ and even if \bar{k}_X/\bar{k}_Y is less than unity due to higher adsorbability, \bar{U}_X/\bar{U}_Y will always assume a value greater than unity.

The studies of the mobility ratios of NO₃⁻ in combination with either halide or halate are interesting. For all the three membranes, $\bar{U}_{NO_3^-}/\bar{U}_{Cl^-}$ values are greater than unity indicating that $\bar{U}_{NO_3^-} > \bar{U}_{Cl^-}$. This higher value of $\bar{U}_{NO_3^-}$ than \bar{U}_{Cl^-} may be due to the high adsorbabilities and also to the smaller effective size as Sollner¹⁸ suggested 'the deformation of certain ions in the adsorbed state due to polarization and concomitant effects, such as partial dehydration' and thus enhancing the factor \bar{k}_X/\bar{k}_Y .

However, when the sizes are almost comparable as in $\text{NO}_3^- - \text{Br}^-$ pair, amongst the various factors controlling the mobility the structural aspect of the membrane plays a very important role. In the two membranes AV-3 and AV-3T (Table I) U_{Br^-} is slightly greater than $\bar{U}_{\text{NO}_3^-}$ but for the membrane AVS-3T, $U_{\text{NO}_3^-} > U_{\text{Br}^-}$. Since the exact structural aspects of the membranes are not known, the details of the mechanism cannot be suggested. In case of $\text{NO}_3^- - \text{I}^-$ pair $U_{\text{I}^-} > U_{\text{NO}_3^-}$ for all the three membranes. In $\text{NO}_3^- - \text{IO}_3^-$ pair, the mobility $U_{\text{NO}_3^-}$ is slightly greater than $U_{\text{IO}_3^-}$ since the ratio $U_{\text{NO}_3^-}/U_{\text{IO}_3^-}$ is almost unity in spite of the fact that the hydrated ionic size of the IO_3^- ion is larger than that of the NO_3^- ion. This is also a support to the Sollner's idea about the partial dehydration whereby the effective size of the IO_3^- ion is reduced and its mobility increases.

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